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Preface to the special issue on the 1st International Conference on Biomaterials and Biosensor Technologies

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Preface: The 1st International Conference on Biomaterials and Biosensor Technologies (ICBBT 2021) was organized by the department of biomedical engineering, Bannari Amman Institute of Technology, Sathyamangalam, Tamilnadu, India-638 401, and held in virtual mode on 12-13 March 2021. The purpose of the Conference was to foster the exchange of knowledge between researchers, engineers, academicians and students about the recent innovations and new techniques in the field of Biomaterials and Biosensors. The conference hosted 98 delegates from 7 countries who contributed with 18 oral presentations, 6 invited talks and two keynote addresses on the research issues of current interest on biomaterials and biosensor technologies.

Nanotechnology based biosensors and its application was the agenda of the first day presentations and major topics for the discussion were low cost imaging using mobile phone to detect and diagnose disease in deep learning and video based gait analyzing system. Video based gait analyzing system to measure hip angle, knee angle, and toe angle has been discussed. The main advantage of this algorithm is reduction in complexity, less time consumption and it helps the healthcare professional to analyse the abnormalities in gait pattern and its treatment planning. In addition, the topics such as the detection of urea in human urine sample using Ureometer and synthesis of multifunctional nanomaterials for the detection of L-Cysteine and water contaminants such as mercury and chromium were also discussed.

In the biomaterial session, the major topics for the discussion was about biomaterials for different applications. A new injectable formulation for the treatment of osteomyelitis with good injectability and allows the administration of vancomycin locally, in therapeutically effective doses has been discussed. Development of air-jet spun polymeric membranes based on Polycaprolactone (PCL) and Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) as highly interconnected porous structures for wound healing applications was discussed. Another important topic was regarding in ovo model showing high angiogenesis potential of electrospun chitosan based multilayered scaffold for urethral repair. In addition, the topics such as luminescent nanoparticles from cocoa pod husks as bioimaging tools, Marine derived polysaccharides loaded composite membranes, Clove oil nanoparticles as anti-inflammatory molecules and in-vitro anticancer activity of iron oxide nanoparticles against human colorectal cancer cell lines were also discussed.

The selected abstracts have been reviewed by Anusha Ashokan, Department of Biotechnology, Cochin University of Science and Technology (CUSAT), Kochi, India-682022 and Arjun Ajith Mohan, Nanoscience Research laboratory, School of Materials Science and Engineering, NIT Calicut, Calicut, India-673601.

This special issue contains extended versions of twelve selected papers from the 1st International Conference on Biomaterials and Biosensor Technologies (ICBBT 2021). This issue is aimed to foster the development of the research on these topics that still stimulate the scientific community in worthwhile discussions and that will keep alive the participation to the next ICBBT Conference.